

Play-Based Learning: Stories of Kindergarten Teachers

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Abstract. Play-based learning as stories of kindergarten teachers was a phenomenological study investigating the implications of teaching and students' learning development. Moreover, this qualitative phenomenological study examined the perceptions, integration, and beliefs of play-based learning among kindergarten teachers in the south district of Maco, Davao de Oro. Using purposive sampling, ten kindergarten teachers chosen for in-depth interviews and a focus group discussion who experienced employing play-based learning in the classroom. They were asked about their perceptions, integration, and beliefs toward play-based learning in the curriculum. Analyzed through Creswell's Thematic Analysis method, results revealed that kindergarten teachers perceive play as vital for fostering emotional, creative, and communication skills in early childhood education. Meanwhile, teachers integrated play-based learning into the curriculum through music integration, roleplaying, and outdoor play activities, which benefited learners. Ultimately, educational management insights highlighted teachers' positive attitudes toward the play-based approach, the need for appropriate assessments to measure student learning, and the enjoyment experienced by both teachers and students with the play-based approach. This research contributes to understanding the role and implementation of play-based learning in kindergarten education, providing valuable insights for educators and educational policymakers related to play-based learning.

KEY WORDS

1. play-based learning 2. play-based approach 3. kindergarten teachers

Date Received: July 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: August 01, 2024 — Date Published: September 2, 2024

1. Introduction

Early childhood is a critical stage for the child's cognitive, social, and emotional development. Kindergarten serves as the foundational stage where children are introduced to structured learning environments where they can develop these skills. Several pedagogical approaches tackle and help children in their development, but play-based learning has gained prominence for its ability to provide and support the holistic development of children. This pedagogical method highlights the incorporation of play into the educational framework to promote creativity, engagement, and experiential learning. Since children are naturally inclined to explore, imagine, explore, and interact with what is around them, this method aligns with their needs as it facilitates meaningful and enjoyable learning experiences. Developmental psychology and educational philosophy recognize the innate link between play and young children. Play has been shown to be crucial for cognitive and socioemotional development

by academics such as Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky. Play is known for its ability to create social interaction and construct learning experiences. All around the world, play-based learning is recognized as the cornerstone of early childhood education (ECE). Play-based learning aligns with children's developmental needs and is acknowledged as a crucial aspect of their growth. As a result, teachers are given more and more responsibility to create curricula that successfully incorporate play activities. This guarantees that kids have chances for learning and development that are both stimulating and developmentally appropriate. However, play-based learning is not without its difficulties, though, when it comes to practical implementation. According to Zosh et al. (2018), play is a complicated phenomenon that is challenging to define. The idea that the foundation of learning is a contentious concept poses a dilemma. And to "engage in an activity for enjoyment or recreation rather than a serious purpose" is the lay definition of play (Oxford University Press, 2020). The Curriculum Development Council of Hong Kong published the most recent Kindergarten Education Curriculum Guide in 2017, and it heavily emphasizes play-based learning. Kindergartens are required by the guidance to provide play-friendly surroundings and allot sufficient time for unstructured play. Due to these guidelines, kindergarten education in Hong Kong has undergone a radical change, moving away from traditional structured teaching methods and toward a more child-centered approach. With this change, students will have more learning chances that are catered to their unique needs and interests (Keung Cheung, 2019). In Homa Bay County, Kenya, pre-school teachers have varying perceptions of play-based learning. Most believe that play-based activities are crucial for developing children's social, emotional, physical, and motor skills. While many teachers feel they are adequately trained in using play-based activities for teaching and learning, some do not feel sufficiently prepared to integrate play into their educational practices. Additionally, some teachers believe that play-based activities waste valuable academic time and are difficult to incorporate into the teaching and learning process (Onditi et al., 2018). In the Philippines, there has been a concerted effort to address UNESCO's Education for All goals, with a particular emphasis on early childhood education. However, there is a noticeable gap in research conducted within Philippine educational settings regarding using play in teaching literacy within early childhood education classrooms (Omaga Alieto, 2019). Comprehending teaching methodologies throughout the early developmental stages is crucial for progressing educational objectives. Another study by Cabling et al. (2020) examined the challenges of implementing play-based learning in Grade 1 classrooms in public schools in the Philippines. Using a qualitative approach, data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with Grade 1 teachers. The findings highlighted several obstacles, including limited resources and materials, lack of support from administrators and parents, and a need for more professional development opportunities for teachers. The study also identified strategies that teachers employed to overcome these challenges, such as improvising materials, collaborating with colleagues, and communicating with parents and administrators to foster understanding and support for the approach. According to Pitogo (2023), children develop new skills and advance their growth through play. Despite widespread recognition of play's importance in young children's lives, the amount of free time available for play is diminishing. One major reason for this decline is the excessive and inappropriate expectations placed on young children. Play offers opportunities for children to develop language and emergent literacy skills. Evidence suggests that teacher intervention can enhance the connection between play and learning, significantly improv-

ing early reading abilities when done correctly. However, there is a pressing need for further research into play-based learning and early literacy. The alarmingly low literacy rates among elementary school students concern parents, educators, administrators, and policymakers, who all agree that immediate action is necessary. Kindergarten teachers are slowly integrating play-based learning into their lessons in the locality of Davao de Oro, specifically in the South district of Maco. Although there is an extensive amount of literature outlining the advantages and theoretical underpinnings of play-based approaches, it is apparent that there are few empirical studies exploring the perspectives, experiences, and difficulties faced by kindergarten teachers in integrating play-based learning into their classrooms. It is critical to comprehend kindergarten teachers' particular attitudes and beliefs regarding play-based learning to inform professional development activities, curriculum creation, and effective pedagogical methods in early childhood education.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The primary objective of this research is to examine kindergarten teachers' perceptions and experiences about play-based learning approaches. The purpose of this study is to investigate how early childhood educators view play, the advantages they think it provides for children's growth, possible challenges to play-based learning, and their general experiences and opinions about how effective play-based learning is as a teaching strategy. Educational policymakers, curriculum developers, and practitioners looking to improve early childhood education methods may find great value in the conclusion of this study. The central objective of our data collection revolved around capturing kindergarten teachers' perceptions regarding play's role in early childhood education. The outcomes of this phenomenological study provided us with an in-depth understanding of the kindergarten teachers' perspectives, beliefs, and experiences regarding play-based learning in education. The results of this study have the potential to influence professional development programs, educational management practices, and legislative rules that support the use of play-based learning methods. These initiatives seek to guarantee that every child has the opportunity to participate in an educational setting where play is acknowledged as an essential part of their learning process, allowing them to pursue their academic goals successfully.

1.2. Research Questions—This study aimed to explore kindergarten teachers' perspectives regarding play-based learning's role in early childhood education. The research was executed to address the following inquiries:

- (1) What are kindergarten teachers' perceptions of the role of play in early childhood education?
- (2) How do kindergarten teachers integrate play-based learning into their curriculum?
- (3) What insights and lessons learned can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were described operationally. **Play-Based Learning.** Play-based learning was a pedagogical approach that emphasized using play to promote multiple areas of children's development and learning (Ndlovu, Okeke, Nhase, Ugwuanyi, Okeke, Ede, 2023). **Early Childhood Education.** Early childhood education is the learning that takes place from birth to eight years old (Zigler Styfco, 2000).

1.4. Significant of the Study—

The researcher hopes that this study benefits the identified sectors of the academe, including educational leaders, school heads, teachers, other stakeholders, and future researchers. The Educational Leaders. By understanding kindergarten teachers' perceptions of play-based learning, educational leaders can make informed decisions about curriculum development, teacher training, and educational standards to better support the integration of play into early childhood education. The school Heads. The school heads can gain insights into the attitudes and beliefs of kindergarten teachers regarding play-based learning, allowing them to make informed decisions about curriculum development and resource allocation. Teachers. Teachers may enhance their understanding of the benefits and

challenges associated with play-based learning, enabling them to refine their instructional practices and create more engaging and effective learning experiences for young children. Other stakeholders. They may gain awareness of the importance and benefits of play-based learning in early childhood education, fostering support and advocacy for its integration into educational policies and practices. Future researchers. This would be helpful as an additional contribution to their references for future research. It would build upon the study's findings to explore additional aspects of play-based learning in early childhood education, such as its long-term impacts on academic achievement, social-emotional development, and lifelong learning outcomes.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—Play-based learning in early childhood education was firmly anchored in the Constructivist Theory by Jean Piaget in 1973, emphasizing how children actively create their knowledge and understanding. Children are encouraged to explore, try new things, and engage meaningfully with their surroundings in play-based contexts. Their cognitive, social, and emotional growth is aided by the creative scenarios, problem-solving exercises, and social interactions they participate in during play. In play-based learning environments, teachers take on the role of facilitators, offering children encouragement and assistance to extend their learning. In order to support kids in drawing connections and expanding their comprehension, they watch kids at play, pose insightful questions, and provide guidance. Play-based learning environments are designed to capitalize on children's natural curiosity and interests. They allow children to build on their prior knowledge and experiences while fostering creativity, critical thinking, and collaboration. By embracing constructivist principles, play-based learning in early childhood educa-

tion promotes active engagement, social interaction, and the holistic development of young learners. The study was further reinforced by Lev Vygotsky (1978) when he developed the foundation of the sociocultural approach. According to Vygotsky, the social and cultural environment of development fosters the growth and application of human intelligence, which in turn permits cognition to transcend its biological bounds. When applied to play-based learning in early childhood education, Vygotsky's sociocultural theory provides profound insights into the significance of social interaction, cultural context, and scaffolding in children's development. The Zone of Proximal Development, as defined by Vygotsky, is the range of tasks that a child can complete with the help of an adult or peer who is more experienced than the kid. The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) holds particular significance in play-based learning, as children participate in tasks that are somewhat above their current skill level but are attainable with assistance and direction from more seasoned peers or teachers. For example, children's ZPD is expanded when they engage in

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

imaginative play because it encourages them to negotiate and work with peers in a variety of roles and circumstances. Vygotsky’s sociocultural theory helps us understand the importance of social contact, cultural context, and scaffolding in play-based learning in early childhood education. Teachers may build rich, nurturing environments that support children’s play-based cognitive, socio-emotional, and cultural development by utilizing the ZPD principles, scaffolding, cultural instruments, social interaction, and cultural context. Teacher in role validates and supports the children’s involvement in a make-believe situation by enabling the teacher to work and ‘play’ alongside them. It is an instant way of setting a scene and directly involving the pupils. Our understanding that children learn through the natural inquiry process of play has a strong basis in research. Anthropologists, developmental psychologists, and neuroscientists have extensively studied and documented this phenomenon (Whitebread et al., 2012). More than a century ago, Dewey (1910) connected children’s natural experimentation in play and the scientific inquiry process. Vygotsky (1978) noted that play hugely influences child development in fostering speech devel-

opment, cognitive processing, self-awareness, and self-regulation. Conversely, play deprivation negatively affects brain development and problem-solving skills (Pellis et al., 2014). Play interventions are widely used as a treatment for children who struggle to develop socio-emotional skills, including establishing positive peer relationships (Fantuzzo and Hampton, 2000). Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes. The experiences of kindergarten teachers’ perceptions of the role of play in early childhood education, vital in teaching and learning, a qualitative inquiry allows researchers, teachers, and learners to provide the necessary knowledge and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that there was a way of integrating play-based learning into the curriculum, a way of teaching and learning development that is very critical to school success. Insights and lessons learned drawn from the findings of the study are essential to learning development.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addresses the specific objectives of the study by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explains the selected research design and the roles I played as the researcher throughout the study's implementation. Moreover, it offers thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concludes by exploring the techniques used for data collection, analysis, and strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study's philosophical and qualitative presumptions are vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions—ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological—form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher's approach to the study. A paradigm is a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study.

Ontology. This study section focuses on the relationship between the problem and reality. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), ontology can be defined as the study of the nature of reality. The authors also assert that the research participants' perceptions of reality are varied and subjective. This study recognizes the complexity and diversity of the realities faced by kindergarten teachers who employ a play-based learning approach. Every participant's story adds to a diverse yet collective understanding of their experiences. My sole responsibility was to use theme analysis to capture these various realities and provide a thorough picture of kindergarten teachers' perceptions, integration, and beliefs toward play-based learning.

Epistemology. Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), the researcher tried to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the participants, I would become an "insider," facilitating a more authentic and nuanced data collection. This approach supports gathering firsthand experiences, perceptions, lessons, and insights, which were critical in exploring the participants' subjective realities.

Axiology. It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher's values that shape the study is crucial. The values which influence how data are interpreted and presented are explicitly acknowledged in the research process. As a researcher, I would handle each participant's narrative with care and integrity and always have the utmost respect for the information they provide. This commitment guarantees that the participants' perceptions were communicated truthfully, mirroring their individual and research values.

Methodology. Crotty (2020) pointed out that "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lies behind the choice and use of particular methods and links the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes." Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures. This

study used a qualitative methodology to explore kindergarten teachers' lived perceptions and experiences in integrating play-based learning into their teaching approach. In order to support the ontological and epistemological tenets, techniques like focus groups and interviews were employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants' stories. These techniques were chosen because they could successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants' experiences. Rhetoric. In research, rhetoric is the skillful and convinc-

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Using a phenomenological research methodology, my goal is to explore kindergarten teachers' perceptions and how they integrate play-based learning into their curriculum. My objective was to gather information about their perceptions of play-based learning, how they integrate it into their curriculum, and what lessons and insights they learned concerning the phenomenon I am studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I seek to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. As the study's qualitative researcher, I support a level of investigation that goes be-

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—Determining the precise approach used in a study is crucial in order to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I was using a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammersley (2013, cited in Aspers and Corte, 2019) states that verbal rather than statistical analysis studies were appropriate for qualitative research. Since I was studying the perceptions of kindergarten teachers, how they integrate it into their curriculum, and the lessons they learned along

ing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions to sway the audience's opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I plan to utilize an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the participants' voices while effectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only makes the research more manageable to read but also guarantees that the interpretations are strong and based on the participants' experiences.

yond cursory observations. My research aims to investigate the perceptions, integration, and lessons concerning the phenomenon. I emphasize the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience in light of the various perspectives shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). My study strongly emphasizes in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives to capture the profound and complex nature of play-based learning. I hope to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of perceptions, their integration into the curriculum, and lessons learned related to play-based learning while upholding phenomenological principles.

the way, the qualitative design was the most appropriate. This means that I describe and elaborate on this phenomenon rather than establishing or refuting theories. There are, however, specialized methods used in qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the varying perceptions of kindergarten teachers regarding play-based learning, how they integrate it into the curriculum, and the lessons learned by the participants in this par-

ticular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009) cited in Aspers and Corte's (2019) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the subjects' viewpoints and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, Creswell (2018) asserted that a phenomenological study was a method of inquiry that described the complex and collective experiences of the participants in relation to a particu-

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017), as cited in Hennink and Kaiser (2022), recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends 5 to twenty-five 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least 6. According to Subedi (2021), larger samples in qualitative studies hinder an in-depth exploration of the study phenomenon. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002, as cited

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations are crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure that I carry out my investigations responsibly,

lar phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology is to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that can be applied to all situations. Therefore, I aim to identify a phenomenon that revolves around the participants' perceptions of play-based learning and its integration into the curriculum. I would then collect information from people with direct experience with this phenomenon to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

in Mullet, 2018). The participants in this study consisted of 10 kindergarten teachers from 5 different elementary schools in the South District of Maco. These schools are Limbo Elementary School, Panangan Elementary School, Teresa Elementary School, Masara Integrated, and Kaburakanan Elementary School. 2 participants represented each school, one for the In-Depth Interview and 1 for the Focus Group Discussion, which totaling to 5 participants for IDI and 5 participants for FGD. These participants were selected based on specific criteria: they had to teach as kindergarten teachers in any of these elementary schools, have been teaching for a minimum of three years, and integrate play-based learning into their teaching. I utilized the purposive sampling design, which was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2018). The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996, as cited in Vasileiou et al., 2018).

treating participants respectfully and striving to generate reliable and precise information. I adhere to established ethical standards in my research practices to protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within

the research community (Resnik, 2020). Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluate my study's societal value by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensures that resources are directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society. Informed Consent. This involves obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after they have been provided with sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research involving kindergarten, I was responsible for ensuring that the participants fully understood the study and their rights. This explanation allowed them to make an informed decision about participation, thereby preserving the participant's autonomy and dignity and ensuring consent. Vulnerability. The vulnerability of research participants pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher, I must acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involves providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent from the participants, ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's procedures in a way they can understand. Additionally, I modify research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these participants is prioritized throughout the study. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, it was essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study and implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assess and balance these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing participants' safety, particularly considering student participants' vulnerabilities. This comprehensive approach was crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research process. Privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I am responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This includes anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures are crucial to protect student participants' privacy and uphold the research process's integrity. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensure that my research was inclusive, avoiding the exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strive to make the research's benefits accessible to all who could benefit from them. This approach promotes fairness and equity throughout the research process, ensuring that no group bears an undue burden or is left out of the potential gains from the study's findings. Transparency. Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception and execution to the reporting of results. I offer clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes in this study. Furthermore, I am receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency acts as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and account-

ability within the research community and the general public. This commitment to openness ensures that the process and results of my research are accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved in the study. The qualification of a researcher. The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience, and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this investigation, I hold suitable qualifications that showcase my capability to conduct research, analyze data, and interpret the results. My expertise and training provide the foundation to approach this study with a rigorous scientific method and critical analytical skills, ensuring the integrity and validity of the findings. The adequacy of facilities. This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guarantee access to appropriate investigation facilities. This access facilitates the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigates potential risks to study participants. Having the right facilities ensures that the data collection and analysis processes are conducted under conditions that up-

hold the highest standards of research integrity and safety. Community involvement. This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engage the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact. Additionally, this involvement fosters trust and cooperation between me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helps to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhances the overall quality and applicability of the results. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors. I maintained thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work was devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries were authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I ensure that the research process is conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I create an environment that encourages the open and honest exploration of ideas and promotes fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helps to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensures that the findings were reliable, and representative of the true phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I am familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as

interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possess the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question is satisfactorily addressed and the results are legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allows me to deeply explore complex social phenomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gather information from various sources, such as interviews or observations, ensuring accurate and secure storage of this information. I followed

ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured that data was structured and available for later examination and understanding. This careful management of data helps maintain the integrity of the research process. It supports producing credible, reliable findings that can be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyzed the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives by the research query. I utilize meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allows me to deeply understand the data, providing insights that were not only relevant but also contribute significantly to the

field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I am tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensured the research results were easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helps to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they were not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that could further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. Data Collection—This study employed a systematic data collection procedure. Several steps were taken to adhere to the proper data collection procedure, which ensured the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. To initiate the data collection process, I secure endorsements from key stakeholders, including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the participants' parents. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step is scheduled to occur within the last two weeks of May 2024, ensuring that all necessary permissions are in place before data collection. This proactive approach facilitates compliance with ethical standards and fosters a cooperative environment among all parties involved. Asking permission from the Schools Division Su-

perintendent. Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This requires submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attach Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and participant identification process. Moreover, I would wait for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step was undertaken during the last week of February 2024, ensuring that all necessary approvals were in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for permission from the school heads. Once permission is granted, I seek approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked permission to conduct the study from the first week of March 2024 to the last week of the same month. Obtaining consent from the par-

participants. With the school heads' approval, I asked for consent from the research participants through informed consent forms. These forms clearly explain the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This consent process ensured that participants were fully informed and agreed to participate. Asking for consent from both the participants and their parents or guardians was done in the second week of March 2024. Conducting the interview. Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide

2.8. Data Analysis—After collecting the data, I began data coding and thematic content analysis. This involves methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulate conclusions and glean insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allows me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the participants' experiences and perspectives. In this study, I employ Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which was particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates categorizing identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis is a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to arrange and dissect complex data sets systematically. It involves searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the data. This process necessitates

to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews will take place in the last two weeks of March 2023. Transcribing the interviewees' responses. Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribed the interviewees' remarks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure used audio recordings and field notes to capture the breadth of participants' reactions comprehensively. The transcription of interviewee responses is scheduled for the first week of April 2024.

the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis was both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep insights into the study's objectives. Therefore, my research used Creswell's Thematic Analysis, necessitating extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there are multiple essential phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I become fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I become acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I started categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I created themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes were examined and improved to ensure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step combines the themes and insights into a cohesive article that conveys the study's conclusions. This methodical approach guarantees a comprehensive examination and enhances the comprehension of the information.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework in phenomenological research was a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I used Colaizzi’s method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their perceptions of play-based learning and how they integrate it into the curriculum. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi’s (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process offering rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, which was validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews were common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore their intricate relationships (Wirihana et al., 2018). Data Familiarization. By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aim to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process is crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants’ statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. Identifying Significant Statements. I carefully identified every statement in the narratives that was directly related to the phenomenon I was studying. To identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step is essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a strong basis for future thematic development. Formulating Meanings.

After carefully examining the important statements, I determined meanings that were pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing was never possible, I have to reflexively “bracket” my presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants’ real experiences, this process entails putting aside my own interpretations as much as is practical. Clustering Themes. I ensure a rigorous analysis that remains true to the participants’ experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. Allowing the themes to naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces preserves the integrity of the analysis. Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporate every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon I write. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it is ensured that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant has had. Producing the fundamental structure. I break down the lengthy explanation into a succinct statement that highlights the key elements that I believe were crucial to understanding the phenomenon’s structure. This succinct synthesis effectively and concisely communicates the essence of the participants’ experiences, concentrating on the essential components necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I asked participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience by returning it to all participants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I might go back and change the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings were increased, and the analysis was firmly based on the participants' perspectives. The following fig-

ure illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to explain the actions taken to comprehensively analyze the data comprehensively.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study was about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results are, ensuring that the conclusions are trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study is. These considerations are further described below, according to Guba

(1981). Credibility. Building credibility entails proving that the results are accurate. Credibility was important for this study because it evaluates if the results accurately represent the realities, perceptions, and experiences of kindergarten teachers who employ play-based learning in their teaching approach. I converse with the participants for a long time to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and increase

my credibility. I also use triangulation, gathering information from various sources, including observations, interviews, and maybe questionnaires. In order to confirm the interpretations, I give the participants a preliminary version of the findings as part of member checking. Transferability. The degree to which this study's results could be used in different situations or with different populations was referred to as transferability. While the particular insights were closely linked to kindergarten teachers' perceptions and experiences in a specific educational environment, I would thoroughly explain the research context and methodology. The study's transferability was increased because this thorough, rich narrative enables others, including educators, school administrators, and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. Confirmability. Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by ensuring that the respondents, not my prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I keep a thorough audit trail detailing every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, to ensure confirmabil-

ity. This methodological transparency makes it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and reviewing the choices made. Dependability. Dependability means proving that the study results are reliable and repeatable in similar situations. This study's dependability was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. By ensuring that other researchers can duplicate the study and possibly produce consistent results, such documentation validates the research's dependability. By following these standards, the research not only offers valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding kindergarten teachers' perceptions of their integration of play into the curriculum but also offers a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhances the study's standing in the academic community and provides insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter offered a comprehensive exploration of preschool teachers in the South district of Maco, focusing on their responses to the research questions regarding their perspectives on the role of play-based learning in early childhood education, their integration strategies, and the valuable insights drawn from their perceptions. The collected responses were methodically classified into themes and structured into sections, each complemented by corresponding statements. Moreover, a brief rationalization process was applied to these statements, strengthened by insights derived from prior studies, establishing a solid foundation for subsequent discussions.

3.1. Kindergarten Teachers' Perceptions of Play In Childhood Education—Early childhood education shapes a child's cognitive, emotional, and social development. Among the methodologies employed in early education, play-based learning has gained recognition for

its potential to foster holistic growth. Kindergarten, a critical stage in a child's educational journey, relies heavily on the effective integration of play as an educational tool. The succeeding sections provided kindergarten teachers' perceptions of play in childhood education in the South district of Maco.

3.1.1. Play fosters students' emotional skills—

Kindergarten teachers acknowledged that they played a significant role in fostering students' emotional skills. Children could explore and express a range of emotions through imaginative play scenarios, helping them develop emotional intelligence. Teachers observed how engaging in role-playing activities enabled students to understand and manage their feelings as they navigated scenarios requiring empathy, cooperation, and conflict resolution. The emotional regulation developed during play contributed to a positive classroom atmosphere, and it laid a foundation for future social interactions and emotional well-being. Preschool teachers in the South Maco district have perceived that play-based learning fostered their students' emotional skills. According to the research participants' responses, activities like 'Emotion Theater,' 'Friendship Garden,' 'Feelings Journal,' 'Story Stones,' and 'Conflict Resolution Puppets' all contributed to students' emotional development. 'Emotion Theater' and 'Feelings Journal' helped children articulate and recognize emotions, building their emotional vocabulary. The 'Friendship Garden' project provided hands-on experience in teamwork and emo-

3.1.2. Play fosters students' creativity skills—Kindergarten teachers also recognized the role of play in nurturing students' creativity skills. Play allowed children to explore their imagination, experiment with ideas, and engage in divergent thinking. Teachers observed how open-ended play activities encouraged children to think outside the box and develop innovative solutions to challenges. Creative expression during play enhanced cognitive development and fostered a positive attitude toward problem-solving and a lifelong love for learning. Preschool teachers in the South Maco district have perceived that play-based learning fostered their students' creativity skills. In line with the mentioned responses, kindergarten teachers play a role in cultivating creativity

tional regulation. 'Story Stones' fostered empathy through creative storytelling and understanding diverse emotions. The 'Conflict Resolution Puppets' activity addressed emotional resilience and positive conflict navigation. Kindergarten teachers emphasized incorporating play in fostering students' emotional skills, aligning with Griswold's claim that play holds emotional and physical advantages for young children (Griswold, 2018, as cited in Clark, 2020). Also, as noted by Taylor and Boyer (2020), learning through play promotes the development of social and emotional competencies. This includes facilitating student communication and conversations, peer interactions, understanding and following play rules, taking turns, handling transitions, and working as a team. In research carried out by Pyle and DeLuca (2013, cited in Graves, 2022), 67 kindergarten teachers who utilized play-based learning reported that it aids students in self-regulating their behaviors and emotions, communicating to express their thoughts and feelings, taking risks, experimenting with new ideas, and learning collaboratively from their peers.

across different subjects. For instance, in science lessons, they promoted open-ended experiments to stimulate curiosity and inventive thinking. In mathematics, problem-solving tasks encouraged students to develop creative solutions independently. Literary activities also involved crafting alternative endings to stories and fostering imaginative engagement, while art classes provided avenues for self-expression and refining fine motor skills. Even in social studies, creativity flourished through exercises like designing flags or inventing imaginary countries. These practices enhanced learning experiences and fostered a greater appreciation for creativity and self-expression in students. According to the Australian Government Department of Education, children's learning is multifaceted.

It encompasses cognitive, linguistic, physical, social, emotional, personal, spiritual, and creative dimensions that are all closely intertwined and interconnected (Australian Government Department of Education [AGDE], 2022). Writing, sketching, painting, and sculpting are examples of play activities that are thought to be crucial for a kid's ego development since they let the child express their own emotions and creativity. These activities are, therefore, essential

3.1.3. Play fosters students' communication skills—In the kindergarten classroom, teachers observed the development of communication skills through play as an integral aspect of a child's early education. Play offered a context for children to practice verbal and non-verbal language in collaborative activities. Teachers noted improved vocabulary, articulation, and expression as students negotiated roles, shared ideas, and interacted with peers during playtime. Preschool teachers in the South Maco district have perceived that play-based learning fostered their students' communication skills. Research participants indicated that role-playing as different animals enhanced students' communication skills through sounds and gestures. The shapes and colors unit reinforced knowledge and encouraged collaborative play, further promoting communication and role-playing as community helpers broadened awareness and developed communication skills through conversations and problem-solving. Additionally, acting out weather scenarios enhanced language development and expressive communication, and the transportation-themed play activities improved

3.2. Kindergarten Teachers' Integration of Play in the Curriculum—Preschool teachers employed diverse methods to incorporate play-based learning into their curricula, recognizing the significance of holistic development

for enhancing their capacity for play-based self-expression (Hino, 2003, as cited in Heang et al., 2021). Also, Heang et al.'s study (2021) revealed that through play, children unleash their imaginations and creativity, fostering creativity and curiosity as well as problem-solving skills. Thus, play-based learning outcomes are beneficial for teachers and students in achieving successful teaching-learning.

communication through role discussions and coordinated play scenarios. These activities significantly enhanced students' communication skills, as play positively impacted their ability to express themselves effectively. In alignment with these findings, Bell et al. (2016, as cited in Walther, 2019) stated that play-based learning enables students to enhance their language and communication skills while also allowing them to engage in discussions about academic content and build on each other's ideas. Peaslee (2022) further asserted that incorporating play-based learning in the classroom supports both language and social development. Students who engage in play with their peers demonstrate improved communication with teachers and classmates, an expanded oral vocabulary, and better conversation routines, all of which positively impact oral language development. This enhanced communication subsequently influences students' academic performance and behavior (Taylor Boyer, 2019). Figure 3 shows the kindergarten teachers' perceptions of play in childhood education and the emergence of two themes: play fosters students' creative skills, and play fosters students' communication skills.

in young learners. Through various approaches, educators created environments that stimulated curiosity and engagement. These play-based strategies not only make learning enjoyable for preschoolers but also serve as tools for skill

Fig. 3. Kindergarten Teachers' Perceptions of Play in Childhood Education

acquisition. Preschool teachers played a role in laying the foundation for lifelong learning by tailoring their approaches to their student's needs and interests.

3.2.1. Roleplaying as play-based learning in the curriculum—In early education, educators might adopt roleplaying as a method for learning through play, acknowledging its advantages. Through imaginative scenarios, children have the opportunity to assume different roles and viewpoints, which stimulates creativity and deepens their grasp of social interactions. Roleplaying also helps children develop emotional understanding by engaging with different situations and encourages cognitive growth by fostering problem-solving and critical-thinking skills. Teachers have noted the positive effects of roleplaying on students' overall development, including social, emotional, and cognitive aspects. The preschool teachers in the South Maco District showcased a comprehensive approach to play-based learning through roleplaying. By incorporating themed dramatic play areas, they conveyed academic concepts and prioritized the development of crucial social, communication, and language skills. The teachers demon-

strated creativity by transforming the learning environment into engaging scenarios such as a doctor's clinic, an ocean exploration station, a farm, a transportation hub, and a rocket ship. The roleplaying activities fostered collaboration, teamwork, and imaginative storytelling in each instance. Roleplay is a standard drama-supported cooperative learning method and a valuable teaching strategy for preschoolers as it supports their learning, social and emotional development, and language skills (Koperna, 2020). The research acknowledged the therapeutic role of fun in play-based learning, emphasizing its fundamental role in children's learning and development. Chorievich (2020) highlighted that roleplaying games involve children embodying content through their roles, utilizing props, costumes, and toys to enhance the experience and make the activity enjoyable. The spontaneous expression of creativity and interaction with learners inherent in roleplaying aligns with the observed characteristics of the preschool teachers' approach to play-based learning.

3.2.2. Music Integration as a play-based learning in the curriculum—Incorporating music into the kindergarten curriculum as a play-based learning approach has proven to be an effective strategy. Music engages children's senses, making learning enjoyable and interactive. Students enhance their motor skills and develop a deeper understanding of language and vocabulary through singing, rhythm, and movement activities. The integration of music into the curriculum fosters creativity, as children were encouraged to express themselves through song and dance. Kindergarten teachers may find music adding joy to the learning environment and is a powerful tool for cognitive,

emotional, and social development. Preschool teachers in the South Maco district showcased a consistent theme of integrating music across various subjects to enhance learning experiences. Music made language development enjoyable in English lessons, aided memory retention, and created a playful and interactive environment. Similarly, music was employed in math classes to make abstract concepts tangible, reinforcing mathematical understanding while promoting movement and engagement. The incorporation of music in English lessons extended to vocabulary and sentence structure, fostering language skills and creativity. Furthermore, the emphasis on interactive and play-based learning in

music classes and physical education demonstrated a holistic approach, integrating music to instill a love for the subject, enhance motor skills, and add enjoyment and creativity to different learning domains. By playing and listening to rhymes, a child who learns best with their musical and linguistic intelligence can expand their vocabulary. All the while, children are developing their interpersonal intelligence while they playfully engage in rich, vocabulary-filled discussions. “Music strengthens and exercises our ability to listen and memorize because it requires us to concentrate.” (Eberle, 2011, as cited in Kjoberg, 2020). In a study by Kirby et al. (2023), teachers used music to support students’ language and literacy development. Teachers reported using music most frequently to support language and literacy development. Teachers

who participated in our focus groups described using music to promote the language and literacy development of their dual language learner students. Further, teachers used music for various purposes, including supporting students’ curiosity and creativity, promoting a climate of inclusion, and fostering relationships. In their focus groups, teachers commented on the importance of music in helping students regulate their emotions and behaviors and supporting them. Consequently, a study by Kwidura et al. (2021) revealed that incorporating musical elements into the learning process fostered creativity through the teacher’s open-mindedness and positive influence on students (creative disposition), the integration of methods and a variety of learning activities (creative process), and verbal encouragement (stimulus for creativity).

3.2.3. Outdoor play as a play-based learning in the curriculum—Kindergarten teachers advocate for outdoor play as a component of the curriculum, emphasizing its benefits for physical activity and gross motor skill development. Beyond physical health, outdoor play fosters sensory experiences and an appreciation for nature, enhancing cognitive development and creativity. Moreover, outdoor play cultivates social skills through collaboration, rule negotiation, and resource sharing, contributing to teamwork and communication skills. Teachers emphasize that exposure to the natural world during outdoor play is important for holistic kindergarten education. Preschool teachers in Maco Districts demonstrated a comprehensive approach to outdoor play within a play-based curriculum. By incorporating activities like ‘Nature Scavenger Hunts’ and ‘Sensory Garden,’ they connected children with nature, promoting observation, teamwork, and hands-on experiences that enhanced fine motor skills. ‘Obstacle Course Days’ promoted physical and cognitive development, encouraging problem-solving

skills. ‘Storytime Picnics’ and ‘Weather Watchers’ fostered a love for literature and scientific curiosity and provided unique settings for imaginative play and language development. Integrating outdoor play in a play-based curriculum offered a holistic approach, connecting learning to the real world and promoting various developmental aspects. According to Jensen (2022), outdoor play facilitates children’s development and learning in many areas, including health, social and emotional, and motor skills. Outdoor play has also been shown to assist children with academic learning. Early childhood professionals spend significant amounts of time with young children. They are responsible for providing outdoor play experiences for the children in their care. More so, his study found that outdoor play enhances students’ fine motor, problem-solving, and mathematical skills in an outdoor environment. Additionally, Miller and Almon (2009, as cited in Lalani, 2020) emphasized that play-based learning should encompass both indoor and outdoor activities. They recommended that half of the school day—three

Fig. 4. Kindergarten Teachers' Integration of Play in the Curriculum

out of six hours—should be dedicated to play sessions, with at least one hour spent outdoors. This approach gives children sufficient time to explore, develop their ideas, pursue their interests, and enhance their abilities. Figure 4

shows the kindergarten teachers' integration of play into the curriculum and the emergence of two themes: music integration as play-based learning and outdoor play play-based learning curriculum.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Role Of Play in Childhood Education—Preschool teachers exhibited perspectives when incorporating the play-based learning approach into the curriculum. Gen-

erally, their attitudes are positive, emphasizing the enriching experiences and joy they bring to the classroom. However, a recurring challenge surfaced in finding suitable assessments to effectively measure students' learning outcomes within this dynamic educational framework.

3.3.1. Positive attitudes towards the play-based approach—Preschool teachers overwhelmingly embrace play-based learning as a curriculum component. Teachers held positive attitudes toward integrating play into educational practices, recognizing its intrinsic ability

to promote holistic development. Many educators appreciate how play fosters cognitive skills and nurtures social and emotional growth in young learners. Their belief in the power of play as an educational tool was rooted in the understanding that it created an engaging and

interactive learning environment, fostering a love for learning that lays a robust foundation for future academic pursuits. Preschool teachers generally expressed strong positivity towards play-based learning, emphasizing its central role in education. They believed active engagement and enjoyment are key to optimal learning. Play was seen to foster creativity, critical thinking, language development, problem-solving, and emotional regulation. Teachers appreciated how play mirrors children's natural exploration of the world and integrates educational goals seamlessly. The impact of play on celebrating each child's strengths influenced their positive stance. Overall, play-based learning was viewed as a purposeful method of unlocking educa-

3.3.2. The play-based approach is enjoyable for teachers and students—Teachers found satisfaction in implementing a play-based approach in their classrooms, and this enjoyment was mirrored in the positive response from their students. Play captivated the attention of preschoolers and it made the teaching process more enjoyable for them. Through play, teachers could observe firsthand the joy and enthusiasm students approach learning, creating a reciprocal and fulfilling educational experience. This shared enjoyment contributed to a positive classroom atmosphere, making the learning journey meaningful for teachers and students. Preschool teachers expressed that play-based learning brought joy to students and themselves. It transformed their role into facilitators of discovery, where witnessing enthusiasm and creativity during playtime makes every day enjoyable. Play-based learning was considered a secret ingredient that adds elements to teaching, allowing students to explore, experiment, and collaborate in ways traditional methods cannot match. The joy was derived from academic progress and the development of social and emotional skills through the sheer

possibilities, nurturing a love for learning, and laying the foundation for future academic success. In a study conducted by Khalil et al. (2022), teacher educators' perspectives towards play-based learning have also been positive, with many noting the beneficial value of it to all levels of education from early childhood to the primary school level, secondary school level, and university level. Also, Erdem (2018) embarked on a study to investigate preschool teachers' utilization of the playground. The study revealed that preschool teachers held generally positive attitudes towards incorporating the playground into educational activities, also reporting that teachers prefer indoor adaptations of outdoor games in their classrooms.

enjoyment of play. Teachers delighted in the shared moments of discovery and camaraderie, making play-based learning a refreshing and enjoyable dimension in their teaching approach. In line with this, Irrizary (2019) emphasized that play-based learning covers critical developmental and academic skills, allowing children to develop complex understandings of real-world situations while making learning fun and less stressful. In her study, the research participants noted that children are more willing to engage and learn through play without realizing it, seeing this method as the ideal way to teach because it makes children happiest. The participants observed that children enjoy play because it feels natural and fun. Teaching content through play makes learning more meaningful, as children view it as enjoyable and can make connections to what they are being taught (Irrizary, 2019). More so, Martin and Murtagh (2017) believed integrating a play-based learning approach into the curriculum could significantly enhance the educational experience for both students and teachers. Play-based learning, which uses playful activities and games to promote a deeper understanding of academic

concepts, brings enjoyment to the learning process. This joy makes learning more enjoyable and memorable, fostering a long-lasting love for education. Additionally, play-based learning benefits teachers by providing a flexible

teaching approach. It allows educators to adapt methods to students' unique needs and observe progress in an interactive setting, gaining insights into students' strengths, challenges, and learning styles.

3.3.3. Challenging Appropriate Assessments measuring students' learning—Despite the benefits of play-based learning, teachers struggled with implementing effective assessments in this context. The informal and fluid nature of play made traditional assessment methods less applicable, necessitating innovative ways to gauge student progress. Teachers faced the dilemma of balancing the richness of play-based experiences with a structured evaluation framework. Finding reliable and developmentally appropriate assessment tools was complex, as teachers needed authentic evaluations that aligned with educational objectives. Addressing these challenges was crucial to accurately measure the effectiveness of play-based learning in achieving educational outcomes. Preschool teachers commonly encounter difficulties in finding appropriate assessments to measure students' learning within a play-based learning environment. The challenge lies in translating the diverse skills developed through play into measurable outcomes. Traditional assessment methods are often insufficient, requiring teachers to balance the freedom of play with the need for structured evaluation to effectively meet educational goals. Consequently, the search for assessments that can capture creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving skills while aligning with curriculum standards remains a persistent obstacle to fully realizing the potential of play-based education. With this particular insight, Irizarry (2019) unveiled kindergarten

teachers' perspectives on the sustained implementation of play-based learning. The study explored whether play-based practices persisted in these teachers' classrooms after initial training and ongoing coaching support. Later on, despite positive perspectives on play, the findings revealed challenges in using appropriate assessments to capture children's learning through engaging play-based experiences. DeLuca (2018) also noted that although research has shown that play can enhance both social and personal development as well as academic outcomes in kindergarten, incorporating assessment into play-based learning environments poses significant challenges for teachers. These challenges are both conceptual and practical, as teachers often find it difficult to balance the competing demands of accountability mandates—such as the use of assessments to monitor and report on student learning according to standards-based curriculum expectations—with the requirements of play-based pedagogies. As play-based instruction becomes more prevalent as the primary method for meeting curriculum goals, there is a growing need for research focused on how assessment can be effectively integrated within play-based kindergarten education. Figure 5 shows the educational management insights drawn from the role of play in childhood education and the emergence of two themes: the play-based approach is enjoyable to the teachers and students, and challenging appropriate assessments in measuring students learning.

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Drawn from The Role Of Play In Childhood Education

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, I presented a summary of the study. I derived implications and future directions from the findings summarized here. My research aimed to investigate the perceptions and attitudes, integration, and insights of kindergarten or preschool teachers of the employment of play-based learning into the curriculum. To achieve my research objectives, I employed a qualitative phenomenological research design. I utilized thematic analysis for data analysis, following the approach outlined by Creswell (2012). In this study, I comprehensively describe the perceptions and insights of kindergarten teachers in the South district of Maco, Davao de Oro, concerning the employment of play-based learning in the classroom.

4.1. Findings—The research conducted among kindergarten teachers in the South district of Maco, Davao de Oro, aimed to explore their perceptions of the role of play in early childhood education, how they integrated play-based learning into their curriculum, and the educational management insights that could be drawn from their experiences. Regarding the first research question, the findings revealed that kindergarten teachers perceived play as a significant factor in fostering various skills among students. They recognized that play contributed to developing emotional skills, creativity, and communication abilities. This emphasized the benefits that play could have on the holistic growth of young learners. The second research question on integrating play-based learning into the curriculum, the study identified several strategies employed by kindergarten teachers. Role-playing, music integration, and outdoor play were highlighted as key methods in incorporating play into the educational framework. These findings emphasized the versatility of play-based approaches, showcasing how teachers utilized different modalities to create engaging and interactive learning experiences for their students. The third research question delved into educational management insights derived from the study. The results indicated that a play-based approach was enjoyable for teachers and students and promoted positive attitudes among educators. This positive perception contributed to a conducive learning environment.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant implications. The teacher participants' perceptions of the role of play in early childhood education, how they integrated play-based learning into their curriculum, and the educational management insights drawn from their experiences. Regarding the first research question, the findings revealed that kindergarten teachers perceived play as a significant factor in fostering various skills among students. They recognized that play contributed to developing emotional skills, creativity, and communication abilities. This emphasized the benefits that play could have on the holistic growth of young learners. Successfully implementing playful pedagogies involves planning for intended learning outcomes. As discussed above, learning via playful pedagogies is understood broadly to refer to educating the whole child, fostering a range of skills and understandings. Meanwhile, regarding the second research question on integrating play-based learning into the curriculum, the study identified several strategies employed by kindergarten teachers. Role-playing, music integration, and outdoor play were highlighted as key methods in incorporating play into the educational framework. These findings emphasized the versatility of play-based approaches, showcasing how teachers utilized different modalities

ties to create engaging and interactive learning experiences for their students. The evidence that plays supports learning was considerable. Moreover, understanding of learning has dramatically expanded over the last few decades to include creative thinking, problem-solving, and socio-emotional learning as essential skills. Ultimately, the third research question delved into educational management insights derived from the study. The results indicated that a play-based approach was enjoyable for teachers and students and promoted positive attitudes among educators. This positive perception contributed to a conducive learning environment. Additionally, the research highlighted the importance of implementing challenging yet appropriate assessments to measure students' learning within a play-based context. This insight emphasized the need for practical evaluation tools that aligned with the dynamic and interactive nature of play-based learning. As I reflect upon the findings of my qualitative phenomenological

4.3. *Future Directions*—The future direction of my study was valuable for education practice stemming from the research conducted among kindergarten teachers in the South district of Maco, Davao de Oro, have significant implications for various stakeholders. The Department of Education may play a pivotal role by incorporating targeted professional development programs. These programs may focus on enhancing teachers' understanding of the crucial role of play in fostering emotional, creative, and communication skills among young learners. Workshops, seminars, and resources can be designed to equip educators with practical strategies for seamlessly integrating play-based learning into the curriculum. At the school level, administrators may create a supportive environment that values and encourages play-based learning. Allocating resources for materials that facilitate roleplaying, music inte-

study on kindergarten teachers and their perceptions, integration, and insights about play-based learning in the curriculum, I recognize the potential for further exploration and understanding of this significant educational phenomenon. The insights gained from my research provide a solid foundation for future investigations that could enhance the situation of the involved group of people and governmental and educational policies. Given the qualitative research focused on the perceptions of kindergarten teachers in the South district of Maco, Davao de Oro, regarding the role of play in early childhood education, the integration of play-based learning into the curriculum, and educational management insights derived from such integration, the following implications for future research studies can be articulated. These recommendations expand understanding of play-based learning's impacts, methodologies, and broader implications across varied educational contexts.

gration, and outdoor play can be instrumental. Schools should also foster a culture that recognizes and appreciates play's positive impact on students' development. This involves encouraging teachers to incorporate play-based methods into their lesson plans and recognizing these efforts as valuable contributions to the learning environment. For teachers, the research findings may suggest an active embrace of play-based learning. Professional development opportunities should be provided to empower educators with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively implement roleplaying, music integration, and outdoor play in their classrooms. Teachers should be encouraged to maintain positive attitudes toward play-based approaches, recognizing the enjoyment it brings students and educators alike. Lastly, the involvement of parents was crucial, and collaboration between the Department of Education and schools may

facilitate this. Initiatives may be designed to educate parents about the benefits of play-based learning. Parent-teacher meetings and workshops may be organized to share the research findings and demonstrate how play contributes to the development of emotional, creative, and communication skills in their children. This collaborative effort aims to foster a shared understanding and support for play-based practices, extending the positive impact beyond the classroom into the home environment. The future studies may consider a broader geographical scope within the Philippines to generalize the findings and understand cultural or regional differences in the implementation and perception of play-based learning. Comparing urban versus rural settings or regions could provide insights into how socio-economic, cultural, and educational policies influence kindergarten teachers' perceptions and practices. Secondly, increasing the sample size and including a more diverse population of teachers across different schools, districts, and regions within the Philippines can enhance the representativeness of the research findings. Stratified sampling could ensure representation across different types of schools (public, private, and charter) and teachers with varying experience and educational backgrounds. This would allow for a more nuanced analysis of how these factors may influence teachers' perceptions and practices related to play-based learning. Ultimately, exploring the policy landscape and implementation challenges of play-based learning in the Philippines could provide critical insights for educators, policymakers, and administrators. Studies could examine the alignment between national educational policies and local school practices, barriers to implementing play-based learning, and strategies for overcoming these challenges. This research could also consider the professional development needs of teachers to effectively implement play-based learning and the role of educational leadership in supporting this pedagogical approach.

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